

Politeness Orientation and Social Hierarchies: Case of Kashmiri Speakers

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Abstract

Politeness strategies vary from culture to culture. People adopt widely shared strategies belonging to their own particular culture. Pragmatic research in general and cross cultural pragmatic studies in particular concentrate on realization of speech acts among native and non-native speakers of English language, while to understand uniqueness of cultures there is a dire need to study variations take place among individuals belonging to same culture due to some variables, for example, age, status, formality level, severity of offence etc (Bashir, 2019). Nevertheless, the current study attempts to investigate realization of speech act of apology used by people of three different social groups of Kashmiri speakers living in Himalayan region of South Asia. To investigate politeness orientation of the respondents of the current study, they are divided into three groups: first group called 'lower', has apologizer with lower social status and addressee/apologizee with higher social status; second group called 'equals' comprises both, apologizer and addressee/apologizee partaking equal social status; and the third group called 'higher', contains apologizer with higher social status and addressee/apologizee with lower social status. The reason of undertaking this research project is to discover cultural understanding of Kashmiris for the people of international community because approximately 0.8 million Kashmiris are presently residing in European countries and Middle East. Data has been collected through Discourse Completion Task (DCTs) and interviews. Brown & Levinson's (1987) theory of politeness has been used to analyse politeness orientation of individuals with different social status from Kashmir- a society of Himalayan region- while the taxonomy proposed by Bashir, 2019 has been used for categorization of different apology semantic formulae/ strategies used by the population under study for apologizing.

Introduction

State of Jammu & Kashmir is amongst the most beautiful places situated in Himalayan region of South Asia. It is surrounded by atomic powers: Russia, China, India and Pakistan and has a long history of 600 years cherishing its own rich and unique culture. There are two major language varieties Pahari and Kashmiri which have their roots in Indo-Aryan and Indo-Iranian language families along with dozens of other varieties which are also spoken in this region. It is a controversial state/ country as half of it is occupied by India which is called Indian occupied Kashmir and the rest which is called Azad Jammu & Kashmir (AJ&K) is administered by Pakistan whereas a little part of it is also controlled by China. This research work is based on data collected from AJ&K (Pakistani administered territory) where the official language is Urdu which is commonly used -spoken and understood- by almost every person thus is working as lingua franca. As every culture has its own politeness strategies which are used in conversation and displayed heavily in everyday interaction, Kashmiris, too, possess their own face wants, face threats and politeness strategies enrooted in their exclusive culture. While study of politeness and speech acts has a long history reaching back hundreds of years around the globe, research about politeness in Kashmir has just recently emerged with hardly few research studies which could be found in repository. Brown & Levinson's famous work, "Universals in language usage: politeness phenomena" (1978) laid down foundation of research in this particular area of human interaction making it a subject of extensive research in the fields of pragmatics and sociolinguistics. Their theory of politeness (B&L: 1987) contains three basic notions: face, face-threatening acts (FTAs) and politeness strategies. According to them, every individual must possess a face or social face which, they claim, must contain two "wants": freedom of action without any encroachment from society- called "negative face" wants, and a craving to be admired and valued by others - called "positive face" wants. Either or both of these "wants" might be threatened during social interaction due to certain intrinsically face-threatening acts (FTAs) which they classify at two levels: which of the face wants is threatened and whose face, is at stake, hearer's or speaker's. The severity of an FTA is determined in view of social variables i.e., social distance, social power, and rank of imposition (p.⁷⁶) which influence application of

politeness strategies in carrying out an FTA. A threatened face caused by an FTA leads to appearance of politeness on the scene in the form of either positive or negative politeness strategies. Moreover, they consider expressions of solidarity, exaggerating interest in intimacy, use of in-group identity markers, promising, informality, familiarity, and avoiding disagreement in positive politeness strategies whereas, an expression of formality, restraint, and distancing as negative politeness strategies. Recognizing relativity among cultures, they (B&L, 1987, p.⁶²) claim that these “two face wants” are shared by everyone. However, what is face threatening and to whom it is, along with strategy preferences are left open to cultural beliefs. To get answers to many such questions, study of linguistic politeness in various languages as an embodiment of societal differences has been a leading research area in pragmatics in previous two decades (Blum-Kulka & Olshtain 1984). Further on micro level, examination of politeness patterns and usage as a result of distribution of status and power within various groups emerged as one of the chief areas of research by many researchers (Brown & Levinson 1987, Holmes 1995). In this context focus has been to study who is polite to whom and gender differences with regard to several politeness formulae.

In the current research, instead of studying politeness in general focus is on politeness orientation with respect to social status/ social hierarchies. For this purpose, apologies—a speech act which encompasses politeness to a substantial extent, would be focused. In general, apology becomes vital whenever social norms of politeness require healing of a behaviour or a linguistic expression offends somebody (Trosborg, 1995) or if a person gets offended due to non-fulfilment of personal expectations, says Fraser, 1981 (cited in Deutschmann 2003). This speech act usually requires presence of no less than two participants, namely one who is apologizing and the other who receives apology. Apologizing is not just a routine matter but engages many intricate psychological and social issues which are focus of politeness research. To be effective, an apology must have some redressive action to ‘give face’ to the addressee. At the same time, it may result in apologizer’s losing the face. Further, deciding either to apologise or not may also be affected by factors like intimacy, status apologizer and apologize enjoy in society and social distance prevailing among them. It is easily predictable in certain situation whether a manager or boss will express thanks to his employee if being presented with a gift because it involves very less face considerations. But, on the other hand, it is hard to predict if the same manager or boss commits mistake towards the same employee, would he apologise from him or not. Such considerations make politeness as well as apologizing valuable areas of academic interest while studying politeness phenomenon from a sociolinguistic perspective. B&L (1987: p¹⁸⁷) referred to apologizing as an intrinsically negative politeness strategy which shows speaker's "reluctance to impinge on H's negative face", H (hearer) does not want his actions impeded by others. According to B&L (1987: p⁶⁸⁻⁷⁶) from S's view, apologies are FTAs which engender impairment to S's positive face. Olshtain (1989: p¹⁵⁶) incorporating these features defines apology as “a speech act which is intended to provide support for H (hearer) who was actually or potentially mal-affected by a violation X. Hence the act of apologizing is face-saving for the H and face-threatening for the S (speaker), in Brown and Levinson's (1987) terms”.

Lin (2013) considers maintaining good relationship between speaker and hearer among major objectives of communication in cross-cultural interaction. Among the elements which influence communication process social hierarchy, or social status enjoys a significant position. Politeness is although a universal phenomenon, its execution and interpretation vary at all levels around the globe. Every society defines it differently which leads to multiple differences in intercultural communication (Escandell-Vidal, 1998). Thus, to behave politely members of each society adhere to some social practices either by displaying friendliness or deference acceptable (B&L, 1978) in asymmetric relations based on social status.

Many linguists like Goffman (1955) Aijmir (1996), Deutschmann (2003) also hold that politeness process or orientation can best be studied through realization of different speech acts like apologizing, requesting, etc. Blum-Kulka, House and Kasper (1989) hold that many research studies conducted in the fields of anthropology, pragmatics, and communication affirm apology as a cultural phenomenon. Therefore, an awareness of the occasions which demand apology in addition to the most preferred apology expressions can be a lens to discover specific cultural features. Brown & Levinson (1978 & 87) recon occurrence of speech acts as universal (B & L), but their frequency, forms and content as culture-specific themes. Speech acts mirror cultural norms and values of any language under study disclosing its usage in that specific speech community.

The current work sets out to explore politeness among Kashmiri Urdu speakers in relation to social status of the participants. Being complicated in nature, it comprehensively illustrates the way people manage to save their own and their addressee’s damaged face by engaging a variety of strategies. Brown and Levinson’s theory of politeness (1978, 1987) is used as a model to assess politeness orientation of the speakers under study. It is helpful to discover whether the strategies employed during this process are positive or negative politeness oriented. The current research work is going to be an addition to the research conducted so far to investigate B&L’s assertion (1978, 1987) regarding “universality of politeness” phenomenon. Its significance also lies in the fact that it is designed to investigate politeness orientation of a speech community i.e. Kashmiri which has hardly been studied so far. Thus, it will help to find out whether B&L’s theory is applicable to eastern societies which also include Kashmiri community. Further, significance of this study can also be assessed in

terms of general awareness and insight it is going to provide about culture and social structure of Kashmiri community which will help to foster inter-cultural communication. The research questions set for the current study are following:

2- Research Questions

- What are the realization patterns of apologizing in Urdu language among Kashmiri speakers?
- What kind of politeness orientation is rendered in apologies forwarded by Kashmiri speakers in Urdu language?
- Does social status play any role in realization of apologies leading to politeness orientation in Kashmiri speakers?

3-Background of the Current Research

Urdu is an international language being spoken in many parts of the world. According to *Encyclopaedia Britannica* there are “60 to 70 million native speakers of Urdu language in the world”. Where as *Nationalencyklopedin's* (2010) claim, “Urdu is 21st most spoken language in the world with approximately 66 million people who speak it as their native language”. Likewise, according to *Ethnologue* (2018), “Urdu is 11th most widely spoken language in the world with 170 million total speakers including those who speak it as a second language”. It is national language of Pakistan. Several hundred thousand speakers of this language are currently residing in different countries like Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Bangladesh, United States, Germany, Switzerland, Spain Great Britain etc. National language of Azad Jammu & Kashmir (AJ&K) is Urdu whereas English is second official language, as is the case with Pakistan. Besides having huge number of speakers, unfortunately neither Urdu language nor this language community (Kashmiri) could yet be amongst those languages and communities which have been studied enough with respect to politeness phenomenon. Further, no research study has been found regarding politeness orientation of this speech community in current research repository.

4- Theoretical Framework

Politeness as a significant element of human interaction was first time studied by Lakoff (1972). According to her, to avoid breaking down of interaction process people follow certain rules while interacting with each other. For this purpose, she recommends to: be clear and be polite. Contrary to that, Leech (1983) established “essential asymmetry in polite behaviour, in that whatever is a polite belief for the speaker tends to be an impolite belief for the hearer and vice versa” (p. 169). Yet, both the theories (Lakoff: 1972 & Leech: 1983) hold that the participants yield towards negative politeness rather than positive politeness during their interaction.

Brown and Levinson, based on concept of face proposed by (Goffman, 1955) presented their theory of politeness (1978, 1987). Face, according to them is a public self-image which every rational social member claims to have and attempts to maintain during social interactions. They define it as “something that is emotionally invested and that can be lost, maintained or enhanced and must be constantly attended to in the interaction” (1978, p. 66). They, further, claim for universality of “face” to the extent that “in any particular society, we should expect [face] to be the subject of much cultural elaboration” (1978, p. 13). B&L (1978, 1987) divided face in two types: negative face and positive face. Negative face was defined as want of every adult member of a speech community that his/her actions be unimpeded by others; while, positive face was labelled as related to the want of every adult member of a speech community to be appreciated and adored by at least some other members of that society. Face needs of both the speaker and the listener may not run in the same direction which may result in face damage or face loss of any of them because of some unpleasant or socially unapproved act termed as face threatening act (FTA).

Negative face of individuals is threatened if speakers do not avoid impediments on listeners' freedom of action; whereas positive face gets threatened if the speakers do not care for listeners' want of approval. In case, a situation emerges which results in occurrence of an FTA, the speakers make use of certain strategies to lessen expected damage caused to the 'face' of the addressee due to it. B&L (1987) have proposed a scale of different politeness strategies ranging from less polite to most polite i.e., bald on-record politeness strategies; off-record politeness strategies; positive politeness strategies and negative politeness strategies. Positive politeness strategies are “oriented towards positive face of hearer, the positive image that he claims for himself” (B&L, 1978, p. 75). The speaker attempts to restore “positive face” of the listener by showing “interest in H”, seeking “agreement”, claiming “common grounds”, asserting “mutual friendship” “giving sympathy”, and gratifying “a wide range of H's desires” (B&L, 1978, p. 75). While, negative politeness strategies are “oriented mainly towards partially satisfying (redressing) H's negative face, his basic want to maintain claims of territory and self-determination” (B&L, 1978, p. 75). They include, “being indirect, being pessimist, minimizing imposition,

apologizing, using hedges or questions” (B&L, 1978). They claim that negative politeness is universally preferred phenomenon by asserting, “it is safer to assume that H prefers his peace and self-determination more than he prefers your expressions of regard, unless are certain to contrary” (p.⁷⁴). Alfattah (2010) supports their (B&L, 1978) claim regarding universality of negative politeness on the bases of findings of his study about Yamani EFL learners. He discovered negative politeness orientation in Yamani EFL learners as they avoid use of positive politeness strategies, for instance, “showing concern for the hearer” or “promise of forbearance”. Conversely, Nureddeen (2008) states that Sudanese Arabs save their positive face by avoiding negative politeness strategies. To avoid strong apology, they sometimes use strategies as laughing, denial, and opting out. Subiyanto and Allien (2012) also find Javanese positive politeness oriented using formal lexical expression (karma) for their elders and seniors. They behave indirectly to render negative politeness towards their addressee. Another research conducted by Ogiermann (2006) about Polish, Russian, and English languages claims that politeness or politeness orientation is a culture-oriented phenomenon because apologies produced in English were comparatively more focused on negative face; while Polish apologies were directed towards positive face and Russians apologies were likely to be less face threatening than they appear in two other languages under study. Gu (1990) also claimed the same regarding Chinese culture. According to him, in that culture politeness is more than what Brown and Levinson claim: it is a societal norm which calls for social reprimand in case of its violation. He continues saying that for a Chinese, negative face never gets threatened, for example, offering something, insisting for something or inviting someone, are not marked as threatening to one’s face. For a Chinese, according to Gu, “politeness exercises its normative function in constraining individual speech acts as well as the sequence of talk exchanges” (p.²⁴²). Bharuthram (2003) dealing with data collected from English speaking South Africans who were Indian emigrants found that their concept of face was culture specific, contrary to the one proposed by B & L (1978 & 1987). To substantiate his claim, he relies on use of word ‘please’ to apologize which according to him is exclusive to Asian culture.

B&L (1978, 1987) categorize an apology as negative politeness strategy since the apologizer accepts apologizee’s right to be unimpeded and independent. According to them (1987, p.⁷⁶) it is an “essential threat to speaker’s face”. Holmes (1990) considers apologies directed towards face needs of the offended person to remedy any offence and restore equilibrium. Many sociologists, for example, Benoit (1995) and Liebersohn et al., (2004), alternatively declare apologies as positive politeness phenomenon having speakers’ positive face as central object because if s/he does not bother what others think about him/her, there will be no apology and effort to put things right. Positive politeness does not only concern with speaker’s positive face needs but also considers positive face needs of the addressee by assuring him, “he is being noticed, respected, and that the maintenance of a conflict free relationship is required” as says Larina (2003, p.²¹²). Among this debate regarding nature of apology as negative or positive politeness oriented there are few voices which identify it having both the traits i.e., defensive and protective like Deutschmann (2003) and Goffman (1955). The current research work aims at discovering nature of politeness orientation of Kashmiri speakers with respect to social status of the interlocutors.

5-Research Methodology

As far as data collection for undertaking any research in linguistics is concerned, a large variety of tools is available to researchers. But, in pragmatics data is usually collected through DCTs or role - plays (Blum-Kulka and Olshtain 1984, Olshtain and Cohen 1983, Trosborg 1987). These data collection tools are of great significance though they also suffer from certain limitations. According to Bonikowska (1988), the respondents of different studies are forced to apologize in a presumed state of affairs, while in natural setting they may not apologize in similar conditions. Additionally, Cohen and Olshtain (1993: p47) also claim that, “role-play forces the subjects to take on a role they would not assume in real life, or they may not be good actors, then it elicits an unnatural behaviour”. Therefore, Rose 1994; Holmes 1990 and Trosborg 1987 are of the view that valid and authentic data is collected through observations in a natural setting that can be true representative of natural linguistic behaviour and can assist the researchers to identify the manner people apologize in normal daily happenstances. Focus of this research study is to examine realization of speech act of apology and politeness orientation in relation to social hierarchies / status among Kashmiri speakers. In this context obtaining record of real behaviour of speakers or participants while apologizing is very essential but reliable data collection is rather difficult and sometimes may be faulty leading to untrue representation of target speech community. Thus, to achieve desired goal, both, qualitative and quantitative paradigms are used for ensuring objectivity and authenticity of data. This is important to mention that Brown and Levinson’s theory (1978, 1987) of politeness has been used to analyse data.

5.1- Participants

Data is collected from students of M.A Urdu, studying in five different study centres which are offering this degree programme under University of Azad Jammu & Kashmir (UAK&K) Muzaffarabad. The rationale behind

selecting students of M.A Urdu lies in conviction that they are not only easily accessible sample but also have a good understanding and command of Urdu language which may be helpful in getting more reliable results about the topic under study.

5.2-Data Collection

As discussed above, a large variety of instruments is available for collection of data in the field of pragmatics. Out of which, the most frequently used are: Discourse Completion Tasks (DCTs), role play, and observations. There has always been hot debate about use of any of these data collection tools. Some of the researchers vow for utility of DCTs, some go for collection of authentic data through observation, while others recommend interviews and role plays. Every tool has some advantages and some disadvantages, for example, many researchers reckon observations highly beneficial and trustworthy for collection of reliable data while dealing with norms and social realities while Wolfson (1976) considers such data unreliable. Likewise, DCT which was initially developed by Blum-Kulka et al., (1989: p. 13) is the most frequently used technique in researches focusing on study of speech acts is also controversial with respect to its application and utility. Many linguists including Jones (1989) count it as the most effective instrument for huge collection of data in little time period. As compared to role plays it saves time by making possible to address many respondents at one time ensuing a more feasible statistical analysis. Rose (1992) favours DCT data over naturally collected data because the former helps to manage context of research. Many linguists including Cohen & Olshtain (1981); Iwai and Rinnert (2001); Rintell & Mitchell (1989); Wouk (2006) and Kasanga & Lwanga-Lumu (2007) used DCTs in their research studies which were focussed on comparing apology strategies applied in different languages. DCT is “a series of short written role-plays based on everyday situations which are designed to elicit a specific speech act by requiring informants to complete a turn of dialogue for each item” (Barron 2003: p. 83). In the current study DCT is used as main data collection tool because only this instrument can help the researcher keep control over variable of social status- focus of investigation in the current study. Social status of participants is determined either by age factor or professional rank they possess. Based on these two factors respondents are divided in three groups named as: higher; equal and lower. DCT used for data collection is borrowed from Bashir (2019). It is based on fifteen situations which supposedly require apology from the respondents. They are assumed to state as their reaction what they really believe that they would have actually done in any such situation if ever encountered. To critically analyse responses of the respondents, twenty students (four from each study centre) at random are selected for interviews to know their views regarding use of apologies in relation to variable of social status in the society selected for study / research.

5.3 Coding Scheme and Analysis of Data

For organization and analysis of apology strategies, an enormous variety of taxonomies is accessible, for example, Bergman and Kasper (1993); Fraser (1981); Olshtain and Cohen (1983); Owen (1983); Sugimoto (1997); and, Trosborg Cohen (1983); Owen (1983); Sugimoto (1997); and, Trosborg (1987) etc. A close study of these taxonomies expose that their components frequently overlap. However, the taxonomy applied for analysis of data in the current research study is taken from Bashir (2019). This taxonomy is based on highly trusted and frequently used CCSARP model (1989) with addition of some more apology strategies found in data collected for her research project. A complete demonstration of this model is as presented in figure (01).

Figure01: apology strategies encompassing taxonomy

The model further groups apology strategies presented in Fig: 01 under three mega categories as under:

Figure1 .1:Mega apology categories

According to Bashir(2019), based on function of different apology strategies, they are grouped under three mega apology categories. The first mega apology category named as ‘*explicit apologies*’ is primarily focused to remedy a range of offences where the apologiser somehow feels that s/he has really caused some severe damage to the apologizee. It contains strategies which characterise vivid, definite, lucid and unconditional acceptance of offence. The second category named ‘*implicit apologies*’ includes expressions or strategies which avoid accepting mistakes clearly but do convey apologetic feelings of the speaker and help soothe ruffled feelings of the addressee/ effected person. While, the third category called ‘*apologies as communication management devices (CMDs)*’ indicates another function of apologies that is to reduce any existing tension between the interlocutors by letting the communication go resulting to hook off the offender. It includes those linguistic and non-linguistic expressions which don’t directly apologise for a wrong deed but play a role in managing conversation and satisfying face needs of both the apologizer and the apologizee. Last strategy included under its umbrella called ‘Some other apologetic tactics’ is “in fact a collection of many sub strategies like *application of exclamation, religious references, gestures (laughter, smile, and facial expressions)*, and repetition of words ‘sorry’ and ‘please’ many times, *offering meal* instead of apologizing and *offering sweets to kids* to avoid apology and make them please”.

6- Data Analysis

As stated above, three mega apology categories i.e., *explicit apologies*, *implicit apologies* and; *apologies as CMDs* developed based on use and nature of difference of apology strategies encompassing them

delineate difference of approach regarding use of apology phenomenon in society. Thus, first of all, overall application rate of these mega apology categories is calculated to investigate highly preferred mega apology category to expose politeness orientation of the respondents under study. In response to 15 situations provided in DCT 3000 remedial exchanges are provided by 200 respondents. Table 01 represents frequency and percentage value of each of the three mega apology categories.

Table 1: Total frequencies and percentage value of three mega apology categories

Mega Apology Categories	Frequency	Percentage value
Explicit Apologies	2438	31%
Implicit Apologies	3193	40%
Apologies as CMDs	2254	29%
Total	7885	100%

The table (01) reveals that out of three mega apology categories *implicit apologies*- second mega apology category which includes expressions or strategies which avoid accepting mistakes clearly has been used by most of the respondents. It is 40% of the total apologies forwarded by the respondents of the study. *Apologies as CMDs*- third mega apology category which is a collection of many sub strategies including nonverbal expressions-is the least used category in the corpus making 29% of total apologies. Whereas, *explicit apologies*- first mega category-which includes vivid and overt apology expressions- has emerged as second highly favoured mega apology category in the data collected for current study. Highest use of *implicit apologies* suggests that the population under study does not prefer to apologize explicitly and publicly rather they opt those strategies which without having vivid apology expressions like 'sorry', pardon etc., convey to the apologizee that they- the apologizers-regret for what has happened and seek apology or intend to express regret.

6.1- Politeness Orientation- Positive or Negative

To trace out general nature of politeness - either positive or negative- prevailing in the society under study, data is further analysed in the light of Brown & Levinson's model (1987). They consider "solidarity, exaggerating interest in H, intimacy, use of in- group identity markers, promising, informality, familiarity, and avoiding disagreement" (p⁷⁵) as positive politeness strategies whereas "expressions of restraint, formality, and distancing" as negative politeness strategies (p⁷⁵). In line with this demarcation, apology strategies are categorized as either positive or negative politeness strategies (table, 2).

Table 2, Values of apology strategies encompassing three mega apology categories

Politeness	Strategies	Frequency	Percentage	Overall value
Negative Politeness	IFID	812	10.2%	22%
	Taking on responsibility	0	0%	
	Denial of offence	167	2.1%	
	Counter- attack	376	5%	
	Minimization of offence	371	5%	
Positive Politeness	Explanation	1451	18.4%	78%
	Concern for hearer	563	7.1%	
	Compensation	1298	16.4%	
	Forbearance	328	4.1%	
	Suggestion	808	10.2%	
	Showing intimacy	1022	13%	
	Some other apology tactics	689	9%	
	Total	7885	100	100

According to data presented in table 2, use of positive politeness strategies is extraordinarily higher (78%) than negative politeness strategies (22%). Distribution of different apology strategies constituting both types of politeness i.e., positive and negative is uneven ranging from 4% to 18.5%, whereas one of the strategies taken from CCSARP model (1989) i.e., *taking on responsibility* has not been used by Kashmiri speakers (students) at all. Whereas, *explanation* (n=1451), a positive politeness strategy has got highest application in the data collected for the current research. *Compensation* (n=1298) which is also a positive politeness strategy stood second as the most favoured strategy in the corpus. Likewise, the third most preferred apology strategy- *showing intimacy*- (n=1022) also falls under the category of positive politeness strategies. The fourth most preferred apology strategy - *suggestion* - (n=808) also belongs to the domain of positive politeness. Contrary to that the least or not applied apology strategies fall in the category of negative politeness, for example, *taking on responsibility* has not been used even a single time in the current data and *denial of offence* (n= 167) is the least

used strategy. Likewise, none of the strategies constituting negative politeness could accumulate more than 812 (10.2%) occurrences in the concerned data, thus are less preferred apology strategies by the speakers of community under study.

This preference given to some of the strategies leaving the others shows sensitivity of the respondents to some socio-cultural parameters including social status; social distance; formality level of conversational setting; severity of offence etc and their politeness orientation. However, the current work is delimited to the study of politeness phenomenon in relation to social status of the respondents. Thus, table, 3 (A) & 3 (B) manifest influence of social status on selection of apology strategies.

6.2- Apologies Strategies and Social Hierarchies

According to many researchers, role of social status during communication depends on awareness of the participants regarding each other's social position and status (Brown & Levinson, 1987; Holmes, 1995; Leech, 1983). In the current work, respondents depending on their social role are divided in three groups: the one having apologizers of lower status and apologizes having high social status is called 'lower'; second group, having both apologizer and recipients of apology (apologizee) enjoying equal social status is called 'equals or equal' and the third group holding apologizers owing higher social status than their apologizee is called 'higher'. Following is detail of application of apology strategies by the entire three social status groups in situations provided in DCT:

Table 3 (A), Application of apology strategies by three social status groups

Mega apology categories	Strategies	Higher		Equal		Lower		Total
		No	%	No	%	No	%	
Explicit Apology strategies	IFID	141	7	151	5	520	18	2438 31%
	Taking on responsibility	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Compensation	587	27	370	13	341	12	
	Forbearance	0	0	0	0	328	11.3	
Sub-total		728	34	521	18	1189	41.1	
Implicit Apology strategies	Explanation	318	15	436	15	697	24.1	3193 40.4%
	Concern for hearer	199	9	180	6	184	6.3	
	Minimization of offence	80	4	191	7	100	3.4	
	Suggestion	260	12	390	14	158	5.4	
Sub-total		857	40	1197	42	1139	39.4	
Apologies as CMDs	Counter- attack	5	0.2	360	13	11	.3	2254 28.5%
	Denial of offence	0	0	167	6	0	0	
	Showing intimacy	340	16	434	15	248	9	
	Some other Apology tactics (for detail, please check table 3b)	220	39	(169 15)		(300 54)		
Sub-total		565	26	1130	40	559	19.3	
Total		$\left[\begin{matrix} 2150 \\ = \\ 27\% \end{matrix} \right]$	100	$\left[\begin{matrix} 2848 \\ = \\ 36\% \end{matrix} \right]$	100	$\left[\begin{matrix} 2887 \\ = \\ 37\% \end{matrix} \right]$	100	7885 100

Table 3 (b), detail of sub-strategies of 'Some other apology tactics'

The of each mega	Some other apology tactics	Higher		Equal		Lower		Total
		No	%	No	%	No	%	
	Exclamation	78	35%	28	17%	120	40%	226 33%
	Religious reference	0	0%	59	40%	96	32%	155 22.4%
	please as sorry	53	24%	52	31%	84	28%	189 27.4%
	offering meal	89	40%	30	18%	0	0%	119 17.2%
	Gestures	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0 0%
		220	39%	169	15%	300	54%	689 100

table (2), shows individual value of the three apology categories (explicit,

implicit & apologies as CMDs) encompassing different apology strategies used by the respondents of the current

study. As discussed earlier, to find out application of different strategies with respect to social status for discovering politeness orientation of the respondents under study, the participants are divided into three groups called: 'lower', 'equals' and 'higher' in addition to placing different strategies under the category of either positive politeness or negative politeness. A look at table (01) reveals that second mega apology category called *implicit apologies* (figure, 1.2) is the most frequently used category (40%) in general, while *apologies as CMDs* – third mega apology category is the least applied one (28.5%).

Brown & Levinson (1978) opine that people enjoying higher social status rarely apologize in view of perceived face threatening nature of apologies to their negative face. While revealing apologetic attitude of people belonging to different social groups it is found that in line with this claim of Brown & Levinson (1978), in the current study the apologizers belonging to higher status group have offered least number of apologies which make merely 27% of total apologies offered by all the three groups. Contrary to that, maximum apologies i.e., 37% of total apologies are made by lower group which includes apologizers from lower social status. It indicates that people who belong to higher social status have received highest number of apologies while being apologizers they extended least number of apologies.

As far as use of mega apology categories at macro level, and aptitude of different social groups towards use of different apology strategies constituting them is concerned, the highest application of first category i.e., *explicit apologies* involving vivid and explicit apology expressions, is noted in the apologies forwarded by speakers having lower status (41%) and its lowest use is made by the apologizers belonging to equal status group called 'equals' (18%) while its frequency in the apologies of group enjoying higher social status called 'higher' is 34%. According to interviewees, most of the strategies establishing this mega apology category are face threatening and perceived inappropriate to be used by the speakers of higher social status- both with respect to official position and old age, in the society under consideration. This perception has resulted in its maximum use by those belonging to lower group (41%) and low application by the apologizers of higher status group (34%). Even, when applied by members of higher group, they have often used *offer of compensation* strategy which according to interviewees is sign of generosity, kindness, pride and royalty in the concerned society. While, minimum use of this mega apology category is made by the members of 'equal group' which can be viewed in context of Holmes' (1990) assertion that intimacy allows them (intimates / equals) many "shortcuts" and "substitutions" instead.

As far as, use of *implicit apologies* – second mega apology category which embeds indirect apology strategies by the members of all the three groups is concerned, its highest application (42%) is made by the members of equal group (table 2). The strategies (table, 3) named *minimization of offence* and *suggestions* are most frequently used by members of 'equal' group whereas least application of these two strategies is made by the members of 'lower' group which signifies social position and role they may assume in society: being lower in social status, they may not dare opt *minimization of offence* and *suggestion*- to deny their offence or suggest something to those who are higher to them in society. Whereas, those who belong to social group called 'higher' have mostly relied on *explanation* and *suggestions* for apologizing in case of any mistake/ offence.

Third mega apology category named *apologies as CMDs*, like *implicit apology category*, has made highest appearance in the apologies offered by speakers of equal group (40%) and its minimum use is noticed in apologies made by members of lower group while higher group has emerged as second frequent user of this apology category frequently using *showing intimacy* and *some other apology tactics* for apologizing to those who are lower or junior to them in social hierarchy. An obvious reason for opting the other strategy called *showing intimacy* by the speakers of higher group might be to avoid use of *explicit apologies*. So, it could be assumed that to compensate an offensive situation and satisfy specific face needs of effected person belonging to lower social status (junior either in age or grade) they heavily rely on it which according to of an interviewee "works wonder and heals up situation more effectively than other apology strategies as those from lower social status take it as privilege to be owned by the one higher to them especially in official position". Second strategy which is most frequently applied by speakers of high group called *some other apology tactics* is actually a blend of different sub- strategies including, "*exclamations, swearing, saying word please instead of sorry and offering meal or candies, gestures e.g., smile, laughter or silence etc*" (Bashir, 2019: p¹⁰⁸⁻¹⁰⁹). Individual values of these constituent or sub strategies are given in table 3(b). According to table 3 (b) lower group has made maximum use of these apology tactics (54%) and their least application is found in apologies forwarded by 'equal' group (15%) whereas their appearance in the apologies of 'higher' group is 39%. Table (3b) also exposes variation in use of these different sub- strategies by the speakers enjoying different social status. For example, sub- strategy called *application of exclamation* instead of apologizing for some wrong deed has got maximum use by 'higher' group (78%) while, *swearing*, another sub-strategy is not at all used by this group which might be a result of their indifferent attitude: they may not feel it necessary to make others believe them. Another unique practice considered as sub- strategy because of its prominent use is application of word *please* at the place of *sorry*. It might look strange to many readers / societies, but it makes 25% of total application of strategy called *some other apology tactics*. Its highest application (31%) is made by 'equal' group. Another sub- strategy found in the data collected through DCT is *offering meal or candies* (17%) which is frequently used by the speakers from

high social status (40%) while no example of using this sub strategy could be found in case of speakers belonging to low social status. Ali et al., (2013) and Alfattah (2009) also report use of this strategy among Arabs when they need to apologize to children. According to them, instead of apologizing in such cases they offer sweets to the kids to make them happy / relax. But, in the society under study, its use is not restricted to the cases involving apology from kids only but ranges to the apologies from equals.

Counter- attack another sub-strategy under the umbrella of *apologies as CMDs* has been part of many other taxonomies (Jebahi, 2011, Banikalef and Marlyna 2013 and Abbas et.al 2015)has got extremely low application rate in the current data. The group called equals is solo chief applicant of this strategy (13%). Another strategy called *denial of offence* which has also been part of many previous taxonomies (Banikalef and Marlyna (2013), Soliman (2003) and Hussain and Hammouri (1998) is least used in the current study (7%).

7- Interpretation

Application of speech act of apology among the three social groups suggests that apologizers who belong to lower group need to be more explicit in their apologies towards their addressees from 'higher social group', so they immensely rely on explicit apologies which embed vivid and clear apology semantic expressions. While, members of equal group rarely depend on explicit apologies – the first mega apology category- and mostly depend on 'implicit apologies' and 'apologies as CMDs' categories which reveal a sense of shared understanding and frankness. Explicit apologies being very overt, direct and vivid in expression might be perceived as a potential threat to the essence of spontaneity and genuineness of existing frank relationship which resulted in its least application among apologizers from equal group.

And, apologizers from higher group make maximum use of '*implicit apologies*' in their apologies while apologizing their addressees from lower social group. The purpose of choosing '*implicit apologies*' especially the strategy called '*explanation*' helps them save their face by forwarding some reason as culprit instead of being blamed as reason of offence and helps them uplift/maintain their position in public eye. Likewise, application of other implicit apology strategies like '*concern for hearer*' and 'suggestions' also supports them save their social image / face and uplifts their position in the society which perceives these strategies as care, affiliation, connectivity and groupness.

8- Conclusion

The preceding discussion gives an insight into cultural patterns and social norms of Kashmiri speakers with respect to use of speech act of apology with respect to one of the variables (social status) which were most likely believed to effect politeness phenomenon by B&L (1978, 87). The analysis of data answers the set research questions as follows:

To find answer to the first research question regarding realization patterns of apologizing in Urdu language among Kashmiri speakers, data is thoroughly analysed in tables, 1&2. Analysis of data in these tables shows that the population under study uses such a big variety of realization patterns that it crosses limit of existing apology taxonomies including CCSARP model (Blum- Kulka et al., 1989) the one- on which is based current apology taxonomy. The different apology strategies in view of their function are categorized as '*explicit apologies; implicit apologies and apologies as CMDs*'. Out of these mega apology categories they prefer *implicit apology category* which does not demand explicitly saying sorry or accepting mistake. So, it can be deduced from this analysis that population under study rarely apologize openly, instead for apologizing, they employ implicit apology expressions.

Second research question was about politeness orientation prevailing among Kashmiri speakers. Data presented in table 2 manifests a clear inclination towards positive politeness. The apology strategies comprising positive politeness make 78% of the total apologies (table,2) forwarded by the respondents. While, negative politeness strategies make merely 22% of total apologies (table,2). It establishes that politeness orientation prevails among population under study is positive in nature.

Third research question set for the current study was about role of social status in realization of apologies. The data presented in table 3 draws a clear relation among the apologies and the social status of the participants. The members of lower group apologize more than any other group. Further, this group is maximum user of *explicit apologies*. Higher group has not only made minimum apologies in the current data, but the members of this group have used maximum (40%) strategies which fall under *implicit apology* category which do not oblige them to explicitly accept their mistake and say sorry to the apologizee. The group called 'equal' has made least use of *explicit apologies* (18%) and is most frequent user of third mega apology category called *apologies as CMDs*. Thus, to calculate results of the current study in view of set research questions it can be stated that the population under study employs a rich variety of apology strategies (figure,1) which cross boundary of most frequently applied apology taxonomy i.e., CCSARP forwarded by Blum- Kulka et al., (1989). Secondly, the population under study is predominantly positive politeness oriented (table, 2). Thirdly, there is a strong relation between apologies forwarded and social status / hierarchy of the participants of the study (table, 3).

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